

Conference Abstract

Are natural mires warming or cooling Earth's climate? - A perspective by the new ACME metric

Janne Rinne[‡], Juha-Pekka Tuovinen[§], Annalea Lohila^{§,||}

[‡] Natural Resources Institute Finland, Helsinki, Finland

[§] Finnish Meteorological Institute, Helsinki, Finland

^{||} INAR/Physics, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland

Corresponding author: Janne Rinne (janne.rinne@luke.fi)

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Abstract

Introduction

Mire ecosystems, i.e. peat forming wetlands, have sequestered carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the atmosphere for millenia accumulating its carbon (C) into thick peat deposits. This has created a negative perturbation to the atmospheric CO₂ content with a consequent climate cooling effect. At the same time, the mires emit methane (CH₄) into the atmosphere, which results in a climate warming effect as CH₄ is a powerful greenhouse gas (GHG). Thus, the functioning of mire ecosystems involves GHG fluxes with opposing effects on Earth's radiative balance (e.g. Frolking et al. (2006)).

Commensuration of the radiative forcing (RF) of different GHGs is crucial for understanding the effects of land cover and ecosystem changes on the global climate. However, none of the current commensuration approaches, such as those based on the Global Warming Potential (GWP) or Sustained GWP values, are suitable for addressing the current climatic effect of natural mire ecosystems. Here, our aim has been to develop a practical method to correctly quantify the climatic effect of natural mire ecosystems as compared to a situation in which such a mire ecosystem would not exist.

Materials and Methods

The radiative forcing due to a perturbation to the atmospheric mixing ratio of a well-mixed GHG depends on the magnitude of the perturbation and the radiative efficiency of the GHG in question. The temporal dynamics of the atmospheric GHG content can be modelled by integrating an atmospheric impulse-response function (Enting 2003). For CH₄ and nitrous oxide (N₂O), we adopted first-order decay functions (Myhre et al. 2013). For CO₂, the dynamics are more complex, and the processes acting in widely differing time scales were modelled by dividing the total CO₂ mass into several compartments. One of these has a very long perturbation time scale, thus resulting in a permanent change in the atmospheric CO₂ content, while in the others an atmospheric mass pulse decays with a characteristic, finite time scale (Joos et al. 2013). The radiative efficiencies were derived from the RF parameterization of Etmann et al. (2016).

As discussed earlier by e.g. Frohking et al. (2006), and also shown by the calculations with impulse-response RF model, the current RF of a mire ecosystem depends mostly on its total C storage and its recent CH₄ emission. Thus the RF can be quantified by multiplying these two input variables by the corresponding RF coefficients, with further refinement by addition of data on recent Carbon Accumulation Rate (CAR) and N₂O emission.

We propose a new metric for commensuration of the effects of Accumulated Carbon and Methane Emission (ACME) on Earth's energy balance. This ACME approach is applicable to natural mires with a significant part of their carbon accumulated more than 1000 years ago. It provides an easy-to-use tool that requires few input data.

Results and Discussion

We demonstrate the feasibility of the ACME approach by applying it to a set of northern mires. The ACME-based RF estimates indicate that these mires have a cooling effect on the current climate, contrary to what a traditional GWP-based calculation suggests (Fig. 1). This exhibits a clear qualitative difference in the climatic effect of mire systems as suggested by these two approaches. The climatic effect as quantified by the ACME metric is dominated by the C accumulated into the mires over the millennia, which is ignored when using the GWPs and present-day fluxes. Furthermore, by applying the new metric with estimates of the global C storage and CH₄ emission of mires north of 45°N, we can demonstrate their global cooling effect and estimate their current RF to range from -0.45 to -0.23 W m⁻².

Presenting author

Janne Rinne

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Figure 1. [doi](#)

RF of a set of northern mire ecosystems quantified by the ACME approach (red, left-hand y-axis) and by the GWP approach with 100-year time horizon (blue, right-hand y-axis). RF is calculated from the C storage and CO $_2$ and CH $_4$ fluxes expressed per m 2 of the mire.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- Enting IG (2003) Laplace transform analysis of the carbon cycle. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 22: 1488-1497.
- Etminan M, Myhre G, Highwood EJ, Shine KP (2016) Radiative forcing of carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide: A significant revision of the methane forcing. *Geophysical Research Letters* 43 <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016GL071930>
- Frolking S, Roulet N, Fuglestedt J (2006) How northern peatlands influence the Earth's radiative budget: Sustained methane emission versus sustained carbon sequestration. *J Geophys Res* 111: G01008. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005JG000091>
- Joos F, Roth R, Fuglestedt JS, et al. (2013) Carbon dioxide and climate impulse response functions for the computation of greenhouse gas metrics: a multi-model analysis. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 13: 2793-2825.
- Myhre GD, Shindell FM, Breon W, et al. (2013) Anthropogenic and natural radiative forcing. In *climate change 2013: The physical science basis. Contribution of working*

group I to the 5th assessment report of the IPCC, eds TF Stocker et al. Cambridge University Press